

GRAPHITE EPOXY COMPOSITE MATERIAL

COMPONENTS FOR COMMUNICATIONS SATELLITES

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In 1971 Spar Technology Limited (STL, formerly a division of RCA Limited) recognized the possibility of using Graphite Fibre Epoxy Composite (GFEC) as a substitute for Invar in the fabrication of lightweight, thermally stable microwave components for communications satellites. Development programs were initiated by STL to investigate methods of manufacture, using Bristol Aerospace Limited capabilities for basic GFEC fabrication and STL capabilities for assembly, plating and test. Early investigations of plating processes and methods of GFEC lay-up and cure quickly led to the techniques of manufacture still in use today. These include the molding of basic GFEC structural elements including waveguides, plates, angles and channels currently manufactured by Boeing of Canada Ltd., the machining and bonding of piece-parts to form assemblies and the final plating of these assemblies. Materials qualification tests have demonstrated the capability of GFEC microwave components to survive the orbital thermal and radiation environments for typical communication satellite missions of up to 10 years. Component thermal vacuum tests have demonstrated the capability of lightweight GFEC components to meet electrical requirements within acceptable limits of drift and hysteresis. Qualified components are presently in use on the Hermes (Communication Technology) and RCA SATCOM Satellites, and will be used on the Telesat ANIK-B and NASA Telemetry Data Relay Satellites.

Introduction

The design of equipment for aerospace applications has been characterized by a continuing search for strong, lightweight materials which provide maximum payload capability for minimum weight. This search has led to the fairly widespread use today of fibre reinforced epoxy composites. The traditional and still the most commonly used fibre is glass, but advanced fibres such as boron, graphite or Kevlar are now seeing increasing use.

Certain types of aerospace equipment require, in addition to high strength and low weight, a high degree of mechanical and thermal stability. Particularly sensitive are the antennas and narrowband microwave filters used on communications spacecraft in synchronous orbit, because the electrical performance of these items depends largely on their physical dimensions. It is highly advantageous then, to fabricate these items from graphite or Kevlar reinforced epoxies, since these composites can be designed with very low thermal expansion coefficients. Indeed, by controlling the fibre types and grades, layup patterns and epoxy contents, it is theoretically possible to balance the negative expansion coefficients of the fibres against the positive coefficients of the epoxies to produce directional composite coefficients of any desired magnitude including zero.

In the design of narrowband filters for communications satellites it was, and to some extent still is, common to use Invar to provide the thermal stability required for proper electrical performance. However, in typical multi-channel communications satellites, the weight of Invar might total more than 50 pounds. STL recognized the advantages of being able to substitute GFEC for Invar, effecting a material weight reduction of 5:1 with no penalty in electrical performance. In 1971 a program to develop the methods of fabricating filters from GFEC was instituted at STL. This program and its follow-on activities have culminated in the production of over 250 flight model microwave antenna and transponder GFEC components, of which well over 100 are currently operating in orbit.

Early Development

In 1971 STL engineers were engaged in a program aimed at the development of lightweight fabrication techniques for narrowband channel filters for communications satellites. Although the major effect dealt with weight reduction techniques applied to Invar, some effort was directed toward the search for new materials. GFEC was recognized at that time as having a 5:1 weight advantage over Invar with potentially no degradation in thermal stability. Also recognized was the fact that GFEC is a poor conductor of electricity, and that any success in using GFEC would hinge upon the development of satisfactory metallization techniques. Table I shows a comparison of typical material properties for Invar and various types of isotropically laid-up GFEC.

Because of the potential weight savings offered by GFEC, STL enlisted the aid of Bristol Aerospace Limited to use its tape winding process to produce GFEC waveguide. Initial efforts were aimed at wrap-

Table I. Comparison of Typical Isotropic GFEC and Invar Properties

Material	Modulus of Elasticity in Tension (psi x 10 ⁻⁶)	Density (lb/cu. in)	Thermal Expansion Coefficient (Micro-in/in-°C)
Low Modulus GFEC	8.2	0.055	2.4
High Modulus GFEC	10.6	0.055	0.8
Ultra High Modulus GFEC	15.3	0.055	-0.2
Invar - Regular	20.5	0.29	1.6
Invar - High Purity	20.5	0.29	0.9

ping low modulus GFEC on thin gauge Invar or on copper plated aluminum mandrels which would be dissolved after cure to leave the copper layer adhering to the GFEC. These initial processes were not notably successful because of bonding problems between the GFEC and the metallic layers, and were eventually discarded in the light of success achieved with direct plating techniques.

In parallel with the foregoing efforts, work was initiated on the development of techniques to plate low modulus GFEC directly. It was felt from the start that this was the preferable process, because it would allow the use of reusable mandrels, ease the metallization problems with complex parts and assemblies, and provide an encapsulation for the GFEC material. This latter aspect has proved to be of great value, since plated GFEC components exhibit none of the dimensional changes associated with moisture absorption in unprotected GFEC.

Success in plating low modulus GFEC came relatively quickly, thanks largely to the efforts of STL's chief chemist (see Acknowledgements). Within six months a reliable, repeatable process was developed which has remained essentially unchanged to the present day. The details of this process include more than two dozen separate abrading, cleaning and sensitizing operations aimed at achieving a strong, durable bond of electroless nickel to the GFEC surface. The nickel plating is approximately 50 millionths of an inch in thickness, and is followed by standard electrolytic deposits of copper and silver up to a total plating thickness of 0.001 inches.

Manufacture of Basic GFEC Shapes

The first basic GFEC shape to be developed was the rectangular WR229 (2.29 in. x 1.15 in.) waveguide. Early manufacturing methods used a modified McLean Anderson filament winding machine where a prepreg tape was applied to a metallic mandrel. Despite the accuracy of exact tape placement achieved by the programmable winding machine, the process was eventually abandoned in favour of a hand layup technique. The hand layup technique is now used exclusively to provide a variety of shapes, as shown in Figure 1, including rectangular and circular waveguide, flat plate, angles and channels.

Figure 1. Typical GFEC Shapes used in the Manufacture of Microwave Components

The plating process places special demands on the quality of the GFEC substrate. Experience has shown that the surface finish must be a high quality with a minimum of pits, scratches or voids in order to prevent acid entrapment and the formation of sludges during the plating operations. Interlaminar shear strength must be maximized near the surface in order to prevent the loosening of fibres during abrading operations, which can lead to delamination after plating. For example, it has been found that high and ultra-high modulus GFEC, both of which have low interlaminar shear strengths, are best used in hybrid layups where low modulus GFEC forms the surfaces to be plated.

The surface finish requirements of all parts to be plated makes it necessary to grind and polish all tooling to approximately a 16 micro-inch finish. Steel tooling provides a differential coefficient of expansion to make part removal possible and a durable surface for batch production. For closed section tubular waveguide, accuracy of tools in terms of straightness is of prime importance to ensure part extraction. Tooling for the tape wrapping process proved both complex and expensive where the end closure geometry had to provide a means of tape turn-around during the continuous winding process. This complexity is eliminated with the hand layup system.

The choice of materials is also influenced by the surface finish requirement. It is necessary to use an epoxy resin system which not only satisfies the property requirements, but also exhibits flow characteristics at the tool surface during the initial part of the cure cycle. Two resin systems which satisfy these requirements and which have been qualified for electroplating and use in a space environment are Shell DX210, available only from prepreg suppliers in the U.K., and 5208, a proprietary system from Narmco.

The choice of fibres and their layup orientations is dependent on requirements of the microwave components. Generally, low modulus fibres with isotropic layups of 0/90, 0/±60, and 0/±45/90 degrees are satisfactory, but there are several exceptions. Certain plates which have to meet a given, close-tolerance thickness contain additional plies which make the layup non-isotropic. Also, the need for circular waveguides with low expansion coefficients and high surface interlaminar shear strengths have led to hybrid composites of high and low modulus fibres in a common epoxy matrix. Table II gives calculated values of modulus of elasticity and coefficient of thermal expansion for typical laminations used in the manufacture of GFEC shapes.

Table II. Typical Laminate Properties for GFEC Shapes

Configuration (Nominal thickness)	Lamination Sequence (Subscript s - indicates symmetric layup)	Modulus of Elasticity		Thermal Expansion	
		psi x 10 ⁻⁶		Micro-Ins/In - ° C	
		E ₀	E ₉₀	α ₀	α ₉₀
WR229 Rectangular Waveguide (.034 in.)	T ₃₀₀ (0/±60) _s	8.2	8.2	2.4	2.4
2.13 Dia. Circular Waveguide (.034 in.)	(0T ₃₀₀ /±52HMS) _s	8.3	6.6	0.4	2.2
Plate (.023 in.)	T ₃₀₀ (0/90) _s	11.5	11.5	2.4	2.4
Channel Angle or Plate (.034 in.)	T ₃₀₀ (0/±60) _s	8.2	8.2	2.4	2.4
Plate (.045 in.)	T ₃₀₀ (0/±45/90) _s	8.2	8.2	2.4	2.4

The same basic manufacturing method is utilized for the production of all GFEC shapes. Prepreg material in the form of unidirectional tape is applied to prepared tooling after a pre-bleeding process to control resin content to between 31% and 36%. For rectangular or circular waveguide, the material is wrapped on a steel mandrel, with consolidation operations performed after each group of two or three plies. The layup is completed with an F. E. P. release film and a nylon peel ply. Plate materials are laid up on steel moulds which consist of a ground, polished steel baseplate and a pressure plate which ensures a good surface finish on both sides of the composite. Consolidation is performed after each six or eight plies, where applicable.

Parts are vacuum bagged and subjected to an autoclave cure cycle to a maximum temperature of 350° F which is controlled to make use of the resin flow characteristics and thus obtain the required surface finish. After cure, the GFEC shapes are removed from the tools, post-cured in an air circulating oven and trimmed to specific lengths and dimensions by means of a modified radial arm saw. Close tolerance plates are surface ground to the required thickness by removing equal amounts of material from both surfaces, thus insuring laminate symmetry is maintained.

Manufacture of GFEC Components

The first step in the manufacture of GFEC components is the machining of piece-parts from the various pre-formed waveguide and structural shapes. Assembly beyond this stage can either be by plating and soldering, or it can be by bonding followed by plating. Both methods have been used to advantage and are often combined on a single assembly.

With the first method of assembly, the parts are plated up to the copper stage. They are then jugged and oven-soldered with a low temperature solder such as indium. The soldered assembly is then silver plated to give the final finish. This method of assembly is most commonly used where metal parts or fittings have to be joined to GFEC. Although such parts could be bonded to the GFEC before plating, they would not survive the solutions to which the plastics must be subjected prior to the first electroless nickel coating. Figure 2 shows a Chebyshev filter assembly which has been manufactured by this method. This is an early design of filter which utilized reduced height WR229 waveguide and Invar flanges. This design is common to the 4 GHz input multiplexer filters presently flying on the RCA SATCOM satellites.

Figure 2. Piece Parts and Completed Assembly for GFEC Chebyshev Filter

With the second method of assembly, the graphite parts are bonded together prior to plating, using an adhesive which exhibits good high temperature strength and an ability to withstand the plating process. Different materials such as Kevlar or fibreglass may be used in the assembly as molded supports or fillers, either as pre-formed parts or in wet layups. The assembly is then plated completely, with a stop at the copper stage to solder any metal parts that may be required. Such parts usually consist of threaded inserts, although in many applications even these can be eliminated by directly tapping the GFEC.

Figures 3 through 6 show assemblies which have been manufactured in this manner. The antenna waveguide assemblies are presently flying on the RCA SATCOM satellites, while the multiplexers are scheduled to fly on the Telesat ANIK-B and the NASA TDRSS satellites. The antenna tower, which includes GFEC horns, GFEC lead-bearing waveguide assemblies, Kevlar support struts and titanium brackets, is scheduled to fly on the ANIK-B satellite.

Figure 3. GFEC Antenna Feed Waveguide Assemblies used on RCA SATCOM Satellite

Figure 4. Telesat ANIK-B Antenna Feed Tower

Figure 5. ANIK-B/TDRSS GFEC Input Multiplexer with Dual Mode Quasi-elliptic Filters

Figure 6. ANIK-B/TDRSS GFEC Output Multiplexer with Chebyshev Filters

Performance

Requirements for microwave components include the need to maintain sufficient dimensional stability in the service environment to ensure that electrical performance remains within specified units. Maintaining this dimensional stability is primarily a matter of designing the GFEC material to produce a suitably low thermal expansion coefficient, since the service environment is characterized by the daily thermal cycles of synchronous orbit. This involves selection of fibre type, definition of lay-up pattern, and selection of desired plating thickness, all of which affect the overall thermal expansion coefficient of the GFEC.

A narrowband, microwave cavity-type filter is characterized by an electrical passband with centre frequency f_0 . For such a filter made from a nearly isotropic material with average thermal expansion coefficient α , the variation in centre frequency with temperature T is approximated by the equation

$$\frac{d f_0}{d T} = - f_0 \alpha \quad (1)$$

Table III shows calculated thermal expansion coefficients with predicted and measured frequency shifts for sets of 4 GHz filters recently built by STL for the ANIK-B satellite. Calculation of the thermal expansion coefficients is by means of an in-house computer program based on the general approach and equations of Reference 1, taking into account the effects of the plating. Predicted frequency shifts are determined from equation (1) using the average calculated expansion coefficients. Measured frequency shifts for the filters are determined from group delay measurements for sets 1 and 2 and from return loss measurements for set 3.

It can be seen that there is general agreement between predicted and measured frequency shifts, particularly for sets 1 and 3. Differences are attributed to filter design factors which affect frequency shift but which are not adequately accounted for by equation (1). Such factors include the highly non-linear effects of frequency sensitivity to tuning screw penetration, differential expansion between the Invar tuning screws and the GFEC cavities, differential expansion between longitudinal and circumferential cavity dimensions, and "dog-boning" which is described in more detail below.

There are several properties of GFEC materials which can adversely affect the performance of microwave components, and care must be taken during design and fabrication to minimize their effects. Principal among these are the high out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficient, the moisture absorption characteristics, and the creep behaviour of the epoxy.

Table III. Thermal Performance of ANIK-B Filters

Filter Set	Temperature Range (°C)	Expansion Coefficient (Micro-in/in-°C)	Average Frequency Shift Δf_0 (MHz)	
			Predicted	Measured
1. 12 flight filters, each 5-cavity, 4 GHz Chebyshev; WR229 low modulus GFEC waveguide construction.	-7 to 45	4.3 Isotropic	0.90	0.95
2. 12 flight filters, each 4-cavity, 4 GHz Dual Mode Quasi-Elliptic; circular, low/high modulus hybrid GFEC construction.	-5 to 38	2.9 Average 2.0 Long. 3.8 Circumf.	0.50	0.28
3. 3 qualification filters, each as above in set 2.	-10 to 43	As above for set 2.	0.61	0.62

The high out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficient gives rise to a phenomenon in square or rectangular waveguides known as "dog-boning", whereby any corner radius r and arc length a change with temperature according to the equations -

$$\frac{dr}{dT} = r \alpha_t ; \quad \frac{da}{dT} = a \alpha \quad (2)$$

where α_t is the out-of-plane expansion coefficient and α is the average in-plane expansion coefficient. Since α_t is usually of the order of 20 micro-in/in-°C while α approaches zero, this effect tends to distort waveguide cross-sections as shown in Figure 7. It can be balanced by adding suitable stiffeners to the waveguide or by introducing different materials such as fibreglass into the corners. This latter solution produces a radial gradient in the in-plane expansion coefficient which balances the effect of the high out-of-plane expansion coefficient.

Moisture absorption in GFEC may produce dimensional changes of the same order as those expected from in-service thermal effects. However, moisture has not been a problem in microwave devices built by STL because of the protection afforded by the plating which completely

encapsulates the GFEC. In the many filters which have undergone development and qualification testing, dimensional changes such as those described in Reference 2 have not been observed.

Figure 7. "Dog-boning" of GFEC Rectangular Waveguide

Creep in GFEC can be significant and care must be exercised in minimizing its effect. Creep results from the fact that at any time and temperature after cure, the graphite fibres and epoxy resin will exert loads on each other as a result of their different expansion coefficients and moduli of elasticity. Over a period of time these loads will cause creep in the epoxy, giving rise to dimensional changes as the internal stress distributions relax.

For any given application the effect of creep can be minimized by rapidly cycling the GFEC over its temperature range prior to service. This relieves the stresses to the point where further creep during service will be extremely small. To demonstrate this a carefully controlled thermal vacuum test was performed on the set of three dual mode filters described in Table III. The filters were thermally cycled prior to the test, following which centre band frequency shifts were determined from return loss measurements taken over a period of 124 hours under varying temperature conditions as shown in Figure 8. The results show that after 66 hours of cycling at an average temperature rise of 13°C, the creep produced an average frequency drift of 0.04 MHz. Furthermore, when the average temperature change was reversed to -13°C, the frequency drift was reduced by 0.01 MHz as the filter exhibited creep back towards its original dimensions.

The intent of the test was to show that frequency drift due to creep effects in filters undergoing thermal cycling in orbit over temperature ranges on either side of the lifetime orbital average would be limited to a small portion of the thermal expansion frequency shifts of Table III. To obtain an upper bound on such creep effects the 0.04 MHz frequency drift from the 66 hour test was extrapolated to 10 years orbital life by means of the expression for creep strain E given in reference 3 -

$$E = b \log t \tag{3}$$

where b is creep rate and t is time measured in seconds. Since frequency drift is proportional to strain, the resultant frequency drift after 10 years was computed from the ratio -

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = \frac{f(10 \text{ years})}{f(66 \text{ hours})} = \frac{\log(10 \times 365 \times 24 \times 3600)}{\log(66 \times 3600)} = 1.6$$

giving a net frequency drift of 0.064 MHz. It can be seen that this is approximately 10% of the thermal expansion effect listed in Table III.

Figure 8. Effect of Creep on Frequency Shift in GFEC Dual Mode Quasi Elliptic Filters During Thermal Vacuum Cycling

Environment

Since the start of the GFEC development program at STL, many tests have been performed on GFEC materials to prove their ability to survive the synchronous orbit environment. The tests which have been performed to date are listed in Table IV. It can be seen from the results that GFEC is not significantly degraded by exposure to the synchronous orbit environment for periods up to 10 years. Not shown in Table IV are the numerous

flight qualification vibration and thermal vacuum tests to which GFEC filters, multiplexers and antenna components have been subjected on the Hermes, SATCOM and ANIK-B satellite programs.

Table IV. GFEC Environmental Tests

Item	Test	Results
Four low modulus, plated GFEC samples; each 1" x 1" x 4" x 0.030" thick.	300 Thermal Vacuum cycles -150°C to +100°C.	No visual defects & no degradation in plating adhesion as determined by tape test.
Low modulus, plated WR137 GFEC waveguide assembly with bonded flanges; 17" long x 0.030" thick.	200 Thermal Vacuum cycles, -120°C to +50°C.	No visual defects and no degradation in plating adhesion as determined by tape test.
Four low modulus, unplated GFEC samples; each 0.5" x 4.5" x 0.030" thick.	Exposure to 2.4 x 10 ⁹ rads of gamma radiation, in dry argon atmosphere.	22% average loss in ultimate tensile strength compared to control samples.
Nine low modulus, unplated GFEC tubular samples; each 1.5" ID x 10" long x 0.030" thick.	Exposure to 400 thermal vacuum cycles, -155°C to +70°C.	No significant change (<5%) in tensile, compressive or torsional moduli of elasticity & ultimate strength, compared to control samples.
High modulus, plated GFEC, 8-cavity Chebyshev filter, 1/3 height WR229 waveguide.	Exposure to 10 ⁸ rads of gamma radiation in air.	No visual change & no electrical change except for degradation in return loss attributed to handling.
Nine ultra-high modulus, unplated GFEC tubular samples each 1.0" ID x 3" long x 0.040" thick.	4,000 thermal vacuum cycles -155°C to +70°C.	No change in compressive strength or modulus, 10% decrease in torsional strength & modulus & tensile modulus, 20% decrease in tensile strength; all compared to control samples.

Summary and New Developments

Over the past six years STL has developed and built more than 250 GFEC microwave components for use in communications antennas and transponders. Some 170 of these components are multi-cavity, narrow-band filters, of which 98 have been operating in orbit for more than two years. All of these components have been fabricated from either low or high modulus GFEC, encapsulated with 0.001 inches of plating and having average expansion coefficients of 2.9 micro-in/in-°C or greater.

Since the electrical performance of the filters depends so heavily on dimensional stability in a thermal environment, it is highly desirable to minimize the thermal expansion coefficient of the GFEC. Thus current development programs underway at STL are aimed at the production of components using ultra-high modulus GY70 fibres. It is expected that with this technique, flight quality GFEC filters will be produced with expansion coefficients of 0.7 micro-in/in-°C or less, roughly four times better than those achieved in current hardware. With such small expansion coefficients, creep due to thermal effects will become relatively more significant, and so part of the development effort will be to investigate more extensively, by analysis and test, the effects of creep in GFEC materials.

Acknowledgements

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